

FORM 1 THE PATENTS ACT 1970 (39 of 1970) and THE PATENTS RULES, 2003 APPLICATION FOR GRANT OF PATENT (See section 7, 54 and 135 and sub-rule (1) of rule 20)				(FOR OFFICE USE ONLY)	
				Application No.	
				Filing date:	
				Amount of Fee paid:	
				CBR No:	
				Signature:	
1. APPLICANT'S REFERENCE / IDENTIFICATION NO. (AS ALLOTTED BY OFFICE)					
2. TYPE OF APPLICATION [Please tick (✓) at the appropriate category]					
Ordinary (✓)		Convention ()		PCT-NP ()	
Divisional ()	Patent of Addition ()	Divisional ()	Patent of Addition ()	Divisional ()	Patent of Addition ()
3A. APPLICANT(S)					
Name in Full		Nationality	Country of Residence	Address of the Applicant	
Pravin Dattatraya Badhe		Indian	India	House No.	
				Street	At/post Ladkatwadi Taluka Daund
				City	District Pune
				State	Maharashtra
				Country	India
				Pin code	412214
Ashwini Pravin Badhe		Indian	India	House No	
				Street	At/post Ladkatwadi Taluka Daund
				City	District Pune
				State	Maharashtra
				Country	India
				Pin code	412214

3B. CATEGORY OF APPLICANT [Please tick (✓) at the appropriate category]			
Natural Person (✓)	Other than Natural Person		
	Small Entity ()	Startup ()	Others ()
4. INVENTOR(S) [Please tick (✓) at the appropriate category]			
Are all the inventor(s) same as the applicant(s) named above?	Yes (✓)	No ()	
If "No", furnish the details of the inventor(s)			
Name in Full	Nationality	Country of Residence	Address of the Inventor
			House No.
			Street
			City
			State
			Country
			Pin code
5. TITLE OF THE INVENTION			
A COMPOSITION OF ALKALOIDS, VITAMINS, MINERALS AND POLYUNSATURATED FATTY ACIDS TO TARGET DNA DAMAGE RESPONSE PATHWAY PROTEINS IN CANCER			
6. AUTHORISED REGISTERED PATENT AGENT(S)	IN/PA No.		
	Name		
	Mobile No.		
7. ADDRESS FOR SERVICE OF APPLICANT IN INDIA	Name		
	Postal Address		
	Telephone No.		
	Mobile No.		
	Fax No.		
	E-mail ID		
8. IN CASE OF APPLICATION CLAIMING PRIORITY OF APPLICATION FILED IN CONVENTION COUNTRY, PARTICULARS OF CONVENTION APPLICATION			

Country	Application Number	Filing date	Name of the applicant	Title of the invention	IPC (as classified in the convention country)
9. IN CASE OF PCT NATIONAL PHASE APPLICATION, PARTICULARS OF INTERNATIONAL APPLICATION FILED UNDER PATENT CO-OPERATION TREATY (PCT)					
International application number			International filing date		
10. IN CASE OF DIVISIONAL APPLICATION FILED UNDER SECTION 16, PARTICULARS OF ORIGINAL (FIRST) APPLICATION					
Original (first) application No.			Date of filing of original (first) application		

11. IN CASE OF PATENT OF ADDITION FILED UNDER SECTION 54, PARTICULARS OF MAIN APPLICATION OR PATENT	
Main application/patent No.	Date of filing of main application
12. DECLARATIONS	
<p>(i) Declaration by the inventor(s) (In case the applicant is an assignee: the inventor(s) may sign herein below or the applicant may upload the assignment or enclose the assignment with this application for patent or send the assignment by post/electronic transmission duly authenticated within the prescribed period). I/We, the above named inventor(s) is/are the true & first inventor(s) for this Invention and declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative. (a) Date- 17/11/2021 (b) Signature(s) (c) Name(s) Pravin Dattatraya Badhe</p> <p>a) Date- 17/11/2021 b) Signature(s) c) Name(s) Ashwini Pravin Badhe</p>	
<p>(iii) Declaration by the applicant(s) I/We the applicant(s) hereby declare(s) that: -</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I am/ We are in possession of the above-mentioned invention. <input type="checkbox"/> There is no lawful ground of objection(s) to the grant of the Patent to me/us. <input type="checkbox"/> I am/we are the assignee or legal representative of true & first inventor(s).</p>	